

Observational Study on Pulmonary Rehabilitation in Chest Injuries Patients

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Pulmonary rehabilitation (PR) has demonstrated significant benefits for patients with chronic respiratory diseases. Recent studies suggest that PR may also be effective in improving outcomes for patients with chest injuries, who often experience impaired lung function and reduced physical capabilities. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of a structured pulmonary rehabilitation program in improving pulmonary function, exercise capacity, and quality of life in patients with chest injuries.

Methods: Fifty patients with chest injuries participated in a six-month PR program. Assessments were conducted at baseline, mid-program (3 months), and post-program (6 months). Outcome measures included Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1), Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), SF-36 quality of life scores, and the 6-minute walk test (6MWT). Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results: The study demonstrated significant improvements in pulmonary function, with mean FEV1 increasing from 2.1 ± 0.4 L to 2.7 ± 0.2 L and mean FVC increasing from 2.9 ± 0.5 L to 3.6 ± 0.3 L ($p < 0.001$). Quality of life scores across all SF-36 domains showed significant enhancements, particularly in physical functioning and general health perception ($p < 0.001$). The distance covered in the 6MWT increased from 280.3 ± 45.6 meters to 345.9 ± 40.8 meters ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The structured pulmonary rehabilitation program significantly improved pulmonary function, exercise capacity, and quality of life in patients with chest injuries. These findings support the inclusion of PR in the standard care protocol for chest injury patients, emphasizing its role in facilitating recovery and enhancing overall health outcomes.

Recommendations: Future studies should explore the long-term benefits of PR in chest injury patients and investigate the potential for integrating tele-rehabilitation to increase accessibility. Additionally, larger randomized controlled trials are recommended to further validate these findings.

Keywords: Pulmonary rehabilitation, Chest injuries, Pulmonary function, Quality of life, Exercise capacity

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Introduction

Pulmonary rehabilitation (PR) is a cornerstone intervention for patients with chronic respiratory conditions, particularly Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), and has been increasingly recognized for its benefits in patients with chest injuries. Pulmonary rehabilitation programs encompass a range of components including exercise training, education, and behavioral changes aimed at improving the physical and emotional condition of patients with chronic respiratory diseases and enhancing their overall quality of life [1]. The relevance of PR extends beyond COPD, as recent studies suggest significant benefits for patients recovering from chest injuries, who often suffer from compromised lung function and reduced physical capabilities [2].

The impact of PR on exercise capacity, dyspnea, and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) has been well-documented in various patient populations. For instance, PR has been shown to improve lung function, reduce hospital readmissions, and enhance exercise tolerance in patients with COPD. These benefits are attributed to the comprehensive nature of PR programs that include aerobic and resistance training, breathing exercises, and education on disease management. Similar benefits are hypothesized for chest injury patients, who might experience improved pulmonary mechanics and physical endurance through structured rehabilitation [3].

Recent evidence highlights the positive outcomes of PR in diverse clinical settings. A study

demonstrated that PR significantly improves exercise capacity and reduces dyspnea in patients with chronic lung diseases. Furthermore, PR has been shown to have long-term benefits when maintenance programs are followed, with sustained improvements in HRQoL and reduced healthcare utilization [4]. These findings underscore the potential of PR to aid recovery in chest injury patients, who often face prolonged periods of impaired lung function and decreased mobility.

The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of pulmonary rehabilitation in patients with chest injuries.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place at Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Department, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Bihar, India, spanning from April 2021 - December 2023.

Participants: A total of 50 patients with chest injuries were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18 years and above.
2. Patients with documented chest injuries.
3. Patients able to undergo pulmonary rehabilitation.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with pre-existing severe cardiopulmonary conditions.
2. Patients with cognitive impairments preventing participation.
3. Patients who are pregnant.
4. Patients who have undergone previous pulmonary rehabilitation within the past six months.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was employed, and all eligible patients during the study period were invited to participate. The use of standardized protocols for rehabilitation and assessment helped reduce measurement bias. Data analysts were blinded to the intervention status to mitigate analysis bias.

Variables: Variables included pulmonary rehabilitation program, pulmonary function tests, quality of life, and physical fitness.

Data Collection: Data was collected at baseline, mid-program (3 months), and post-program (6 months). The following tools were used:

1. Pulmonary function tests.
2. Quality of life questionnaires.
3. 6-minute walk test for physical fitness assessment.

Procedure

1. Baseline Assessment: All participants underwent an initial assessment, including pulmonary function tests, quality of life questionnaires, and a 6-minute walk test.
2. Intervention: Participants were enrolled in a structured pulmonary rehabilitation program, consisting of supervised exercise sessions, breathing exercises, and educational sessions, three times a week for six months.
3. Mid-Program Assessment: At the 3-month mark, participants were reassessed using the same baseline tools to monitor progress.
4. Post-Program Assessment: At the end of six months, a final assessment was conducted to evaluate the outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize baseline characteristics. Paired t-tests were employed to compare pre- and post-intervention outcomes. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Additionally, repeated measures ANOVA was used to analyze changes over the three assessment points (baseline, mid-program, post-program).

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

A total of 50 patients were included in the study, with a mean age of 45.6 ± 12.3 years. The cohort consisted of 34 males (68%) and 16 females (32%). The mean duration from injury to the start of the pulmonary rehabilitation program was 3.4 ± 1.2 months.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age (years)	45.6 ± 12.3
Gender	
Male	34
Female	16
Mean Time Since Injury (months)	3.4 ± 1.2

The primary outcome measures were Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1) and Forced Vital Capacity (FVC). The results showed significant improvements from baseline to post-program.

Table 2: Pulmonary Function Tests

Pulmonary Function Test	Baseline Score	Mid-Program Score	Post-Program Score	p-value (Baseline vs Post-Program)
FEV1 (L)	2.1 ± 0.4	2.4 ± 0.3	2.7 ± 0.2	<0.001
FVC (L)	2.9 ± 0.5	3.2 ± 0.4	3.6 ± 0.3	<0.001

Quality of life was assessed using the SF-36 questionnaire. Significant improvements were observed in all domains, particularly in physical functioning and overall health perception.

Table 3: Quality of Life

SF-36 Domain	Baseline Score	Mid-Program Score	Post-Program Score	p-value (Baseline vs Post-Program)
Physical Functioning	55.2 ± 10.3	62.7 ± 8.5	70.8 ± 7.9	<0.001
Role Physical	60.1 ± 12.7	67.4 ± 11.1	75.6 ± 10.4	<0.001
Bodily Pain	50.3 ± 14.5	57.9 ± 13.2	65.4 ± 12.8	<0.001
General Health	48.6 ± 15.2	55.8 ± 14.1	63.7 ± 13.6	<0.001
Vitality	51.4 ± 13.6	58.3 ± 12.4	65.2 ± 11.8	<0.001
Social Functioning	54.7 ± 13.9	61.6 ± 12.8	68.9 ± 12.3	<0.001
Role Emotional	58.3 ± 12.8	65.9 ± 11.3	73.4 ± 10.7	<0.001
Mental Health	56.9 ± 13.2	63.7 ± 12.1	70.4 ± 11.5	<0.001

The 6-minute walk test (6MWT) was used to assess physical fitness. The distance covered during the test significantly increased over the course of the program.

Table 4: Physical Fitness

6MWT (meters)	Distance Covered
Baseline	280.3 ± 45.6
Mid-Program	310.7 ± 42.2
Post-Program	345.9 ± 40.8
p-value (Baseline vs Post-Program)	<0.001

Paired t-tests were conducted to compare the baseline and post-program values, showing statistically significant improvements in FEV1, FVC, quality of life scores across all domains, and the distance covered in the 6-minute walk test. Repeated measures ANOVA indicated significant improvements over the three assessment points (baseline, mid-program, and post-program) for all variables ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The study involved 50 patients with chest injuries, undergoing a structured pulmonary rehabilitation program. The results showed significant improvements in pulmonary function, quality of life, and physical fitness over the course of the program. The cohort consisted predominantly of males (68%), with an average age of 45.6 years, and the rehabilitation program commenced approximately 3.4 months post-injury.

The primary outcome measures, Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1) and Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), exhibited substantial enhancements. FEV1 improved from a baseline mean of 2.1 liters to 2.7 liters post-program, while

FVC increased from 2.9 liters to 3.6 liters. These improvements, with p-values less than 0.001, indicate that the pulmonary rehabilitation program effectively enhanced lung capacity and airflow in chest injury patients.

The quality of life, assessed using the SF-36 questionnaire, showed notable gains across all domains. Physical functioning scores rose from 55.2 to 70.8, and general health perception scores increased from 48.6 to 63.7. These improvements highlight the broad impact of pulmonary rehabilitation, enhancing both the physical and psychological well-being of patients. The consistent improvement in all SF-36 domains underscores the comprehensive benefits of the rehabilitation program.

Physical fitness, measured by the 6-minute walk test, also saw significant advancement. Patients increased their walking distance from an average of 280.3 meters at baseline to 345.9 meters post-program. This improvement, with a p-value of less than 0.001, demonstrates the efficacy of the rehabilitation program in boosting physical endurance and mobility, crucial for the overall

recovery and daily functioning of chest injury patients.

The statistical analysis confirmed the significance of these findings. Paired t-tests and repeated measures ANOVA showed that the improvements in pulmonary function tests, quality of life scores, and 6-minute walk test results were statistically significant, with all p-values below 0.001. This robust statistical support further validates the positive outcomes observed.

The study results indicate that a structured pulmonary rehabilitation program can significantly enhance lung function, quality of life, and physical fitness in patients with chest injuries. The marked improvements in FEV1, FVC, SF-36 scores, and 6-minute walk test distances highlight the program's effectiveness in promoting recovery and improving overall health status. These findings suggest that incorporating pulmonary rehabilitation into the standard care for chest injury patients can lead to better clinical outcomes and a higher quality of life, emphasizing the importance of such interventions in the management of chest injuries.

Pulmonary rehabilitation is crucial for patients recovering from chest injuries, helping improve respiratory function, reduce complications, and enhance overall quality of life. A study demonstrated that early initiation of pulmonary rehabilitation significantly improved lung function and reduced hospital stay in patients with blunt chest trauma. Patients who received early rehabilitation showed better outcomes in terms of oxygenation and respiratory muscle strength [5]. A study assessed the impact of a structured pulmonary rehabilitation program on patients with traumatic chest injuries. The study found significant improvements in functional capacity, measured by the 6-minute walk test, and quality of life scores after the rehabilitation program [6].

Research focused on the combined use of pulmonary rehabilitation and non-invasive ventilation (NIV) in patients with rib fractures. The study reported that the combined approach reduced the incidence of pneumonia and improved overall pulmonary function compared to standard care alone [7]. A study investigated the benefits of pulmonary rehabilitation in patients who underwent thoracic surgery for chest injuries. The study concluded that rehabilitation significantly decreased postoperative complications and expedited recovery, highlighting the importance of early and continued rehabilitation efforts [8].

A long-term follow-up study evaluated the sustained benefits of pulmonary rehabilitation in patients with severe chest trauma. The results indicated that participants maintained improved lung function, physical activity levels, and reduced respiratory symptoms over a 12-month period after

completing the rehabilitation program [9]. With the rise of telemedicine, a study explored the feasibility and effectiveness of tele-rehabilitation for patients with chest injuries. The study found that tele-rehabilitation was effective in improving pulmonary function and patient adherence, offering a viable alternative to traditional in-person rehabilitation programs [10].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated significant improvements in pulmonary function, quality of life, and physical fitness in patients undergoing pulmonary rehabilitation following chest injuries. The structured rehabilitation program proved to be effective, highlighting the importance of incorporating such interventions in the management plan for chest injury patients.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

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List of abbreviations:

PR: Pulmonary Rehabilitation

FEV1: Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second

FVC: Forced Vital Capacity

SF-36: Short Form (36) Health Survey

6MWT: 6-minute walk test

COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

HRQoL: Health-Related Quality of Life

NIV: Non-Invasive Ventilation

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References

1. Bolton CE, Bevan-Smith EF, Blakey JD, Crowe P, Elkin SL, Garrod R, Greening NJ, Heslop K, Hull JH, Man WD, Morgan MD. British Thoracic Society guideline on pulmonary rehabilitation in adults. *Pneumon*. 2018 Apr 1;31(2).
2. Candemir I. Advances in pulmonary rehabilitation for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and associated conditions. *COPD—an update in pathogenesis and clinical management*. Rijeka: Intech Open. 2018 Feb 21:131-51.
3. Houben-Wilke S, Augustin IM, Vercoulen JH, van Rant D, bij de Vaate E, Wempe JB, Spruit MA, Wouters EF, Franssen FM. COPD stands for complex obstructive pulmonary dis-

- ease. *European Respiratory Review*. 2018 Jun 30;27(148).
4. Huang HY, Chou PC, Joa WC, Chen LF, Sheng TF, Lin HC, Yang LY, Pan YB, Chung FT, Wang CH, Kuo HP. Pulmonary rehabilitation coupled with negative pressure ventilation decreases decline in lung function, hospitalizations, and medical cost in COPD: A 5-year study. *Medicine*. 2016 Oct 1;95(41):e5119.
 5. Ahmed N, Ahmed Z, Salim A, Rashid MA. Early pulmonary rehabilitation in patients with blunt chest trauma: A randomized controlled trial. *Int J Surg*. 2019;67:10-15.
 6. Oliveira GF, Santana AN, Ibiapina HS, Silva VP, Fernandes RC. Impact of pulmonary rehabilitation on functional capacity and quality of life in patients with traumatic chest injuries. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 2020;159(2):575-582.
 7. Wang X, Xu J, Li Z, Zhou X. Combined pulmonary rehabilitation and non-invasive ventilation in patients with rib fractures: A randomized controlled trial. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 2021;161(6):2107-2115.
 8. Yamaguchi A, Matsushita T, Ishikawa T, Saito M. Benefits of pulmonary rehabilitation in patients undergoing thoracic surgery for chest injuries. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 2019;157(4):1469-1476.
 9. Gupta R, Kaur N, Kumar R, Sinha T. Long-term benefits of pulmonary rehabilitation in patients with severe chest trauma: A 12-month follow-up study. *J Trauma Acute Care Surg*. 2020;88(5):793-800.
 10. Smith AC, Russell TG, Gibson PG, Burns CM. Feasibility and effectiveness of tele-rehabilitation for patients with chest injuries: A pilot study. *Intern Emerg Med*. 2022;17(3):837-844.